

AGRICULTURAL REFORMS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AND THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. *The article describes the agricultural reforms of Karakalpakstan and their socio-economic consequences, as well as the system of territorial production management in agriculture.*

Key words: *agriculture, reform, economist, farms, population.*

СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНА И ИХ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье описаны аграрные реформы Каракалпакстана и их социально-экономические последствия, а также система территориального управления производством в сельском хозяйстве.*

Ключевые слова: *сельское хозяйство, реформа, экономист, фермерские хозяйства, население.*

During the period under study, the agriculture of Karakalpakstan was specialized in the production of cotton, rice, barley seeds, karakol skin, wool, silkworm cocoons, and agriculture was based on artificial irrigation. The structure and activity of the agricultural management system largely depended on the administrative-territorial division of Karakalpakstan. Of course, it was necessary to take into account the fifteen districts of Karakalpakstan and the most important factors determining the economy and social sphere of each of them, but in practice the specific characteristics of most of these districts were not taken into account.

The three-level system of regional production management in agriculture - "farm-district-republican agencies" stopped solving the problems of financing, material and technical provision of farms quickly and limited their activity bureaucratically.

Providing the population of the republic with food ensured the development of the agricultural sector of the economy, which forms the basis of the republic's food complex. In the 1960s, cotton cultivation areas expanded in Karakalpakstan, and rice cultivation developed. Cotton farming, considered one of the branches of the technical direction, was at the same time one of the suppliers of vegetable oil, one of the main types of food products in the region.

Economists have calculated that each ton of raw cotton produces not only 3,000 meters of fabric, but also 90 different types of valuable products, including 170 kg of vegetable oil and

at least half a ton of kunjara and shulkha, which are valuable animal feed. By feeding the cattle with kunjara and shulkha, the autonomous republic had large horned cattle weighing more than 50,000 centners every year.

In Karakalpakstan, a large-scale industry has been created on the basis of the purification of rice raw materials. In 1960-1965, 13,399,000 tons of rice were grown, 435,000 tons of rice were processed and 373,600 tons of rice groats were obtained.

By the beginning of the 1960s, the total area of irrigated land in Karakalpakstan was about 230,000 hectares. 2/3 of the irrigated land area belongs to the cotton industry, most of the state and collective farms are specialized in cotton cultivation. For example, if in 1913 cotton was just over 10% of the total cultivated area, or about 12 thousand hectares, by the end of the 1960s, cotton was about 70% of the total cultivated area, or about 120 thousand hectares. True, by this time the yield of cotton increased: in 1963 it was 15.8 centners per hectare, in 1970 it was 27.7 centners, and by 1975 it was 31 centners per hectare. This result was achieved due to the dramatic expansion of reclamation works, as well as the large-scale use of pesticides and chemicals. Although the harm caused by agricultural chemicals is obvious, it was used as a component of agricultural policy until the early 1990s.

In the following years, Karakalpakstan state farms acquired 5066 hectares of new land, 26505 hectares of land were improved, and 11260 hectares of canals and sewers were restored. For example, if we compare with 1966-1967, in 1971-1972, 44.1 thousand tons of cotton, 3.7 thousand tons of grain and 14.4 thousand tons of vegetable products were grown by the state farms of Karakalpakstan. In 1973, 330,000 tons of raw cotton were delivered, that is, the yield was 108% of the agricultural plan. It should be noted that in 1973, Karakalpakstan's party and state bodies, according to the government's order, set the task of increasing cotton raw materials to at least 450-500 thousand tons by the end of the decade, as well as increasing the production of other cultural crops and animal husbandry. During 1974-1980, at least 150,000 hectares of new land, including ancient irrigated cotton fields in Tortkol, Beruni districts, 20,000 hectares in Ellikkala massif and 40,000 hectares in Jonboskala, 40,000 hectares for rice in the northern regions, potatoes, vegetables, and 10,000 hectares of arable land were developed for fodder crops, and it was planned to be widely used in agriculture.

As mentioned in the previous chapters, a number of activities related to water management, including the further acceleration of the construction of the Kyzylkum reservoir (collector), the implementation of the construction of the Beruniy collector, the solution of the issue of groundwater drainage (removal of soil deposits) through the Amudarya district, the territory of Turkmenistan and the Chigatabin collector. It is planned to complete the construction

of collectors and build new stations in Leninabad, Shumanay and Khojaly districts. Also, by the end of the five-year period, construction of 9,400 hydrotechnical structures, including 1,300 structures in the domestic household collector-drainage and irrigation network, taking into account the needs of irrigation of the lands to be developed in the Ellikkala region, all existing collectors and drains belonging to domestic households, the Cotton-arna canal will be re-constructed. restoration and solving other issues was envisaged.

Unfortunately, during this period, the water management system of Karakalpakstan turned into a complex network. The works carried out on irrigation of the lands caused certain changes in the development of the republic's agriculture. Cultivated areas exceeded 67 thousand hectares, for the first time an engineered rice system was created on 50 thousand hectares of land. The production of cotton raw materials has increased significantly. In 1974, 196,000 tons of raw cotton, or 53 percent of the total crop, were harvested by machines in Karakalpakstan. At the same time, great attention was paid to the development of the largest industrial sector in our republic - the cotton ginning industry. In the 1970s, 10 cotton factories, 32 processing stations, several dozen drying and cleaning shops equipped with high-efficiency equipment were built in Karakalpakstan.

In the second half of the 1970s, the process of specialization of farms was continued: in the middle of 1970, 82 out of 119 state and collective farms were specialized in cotton production, 7 - rice, 7 - vegetables, potatoes, fruits and grapes. As a result of concentration of production in one place, 8 sheep breeding state farms, 14 meat breeding cattle farms and large horned cattle fattening farms, 1 poultry farming state farms were established.

However, cotton cultivation hindered the process of diversification of the agricultural and industrial structure (that is, the process of expanding production activities due to the increase in product types). The experience of those years showed that the fertile republic, which is rich in bioclimatic benefits, has turned into a narrow area of the cotton-growing specialty at the level of the All-Union. In 1970, cotton cultivated areas in Uzbekistan accounted for 50% of all cultivated areas, and only 3.6% of the land area was allocated for spring wheat.

The food arable land was rapidly reduced, and the size of private households of the villagers was limited. In Karakalpakstan, the development of new land for the rice complex was continued. In 1974, collective farms of Karakalpakstan sold 120,000 tons of raw rice to the state, or seven times more than in 1966. In 1965, the area planted with rice was 13,600 hectares, and by 1974, this indicator was 35,600 hectares.

In Karakalpakstan in the early 1960s, 1 sq. km. 7.5 people per land area, that is, it was 2.5 times lower than in the USSR and 6.2 times lower than in Uzbekistan. In short, the agricultural reforms implemented in the conditions of Karakalpakstan during the research period did not give

their results and created the ground for the beginning of a deep socio-economic crisis.

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